

Analysis of Patterns in TV Commercials that Recognize NGO Image

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Abstract—The purpose of this research is to analyze the pattern of television commercials and how they encourage non-governmental organizations to build their image in Thailand. It realizes how public relations can impact an organization's image. It is a truth that bad public relations management can cause hurt a reputation. On the other hand, a very small amount of work in public relations helps your organization to be recognized broadly and eventually accepted even wider. The main idea in this paper is to study and analyze patterns of television commercials that could impact non-governmental organization's images in a greater way. This research uses questionnaires and content analysis to summarize results. The findings show the aspects of how patterns of television commercials that are suited to non-governmental organization work in Thailand. It will be useful for any non-governmental organization that wishes to build their image through television commercials and also for further work based on this research.

Keywords—Television Commercial (TVC), Organization Image, Non-Governmental Organization: NGO, Public Relation.

I. INTRODUCTION

PUBLIC relations are a powerful tool to builds an organization's image. It also helps the organization to deliver messages to targets, to provide knowledge and understanding, guide, build a positive attitude towards the audience, support and strengthen the credibility of the organization and correct misinterpretation between people and organizations. It said that public relations allows for successful operation of the organization unless it is a job that requires an ingenious approach continuously, which is not easy in a short time.

In phase, if an organization provides a way to create a good image properly, it can maintain their target audience in the long run. There are many ways to deliver messages to target groups and various media such as printing, radio, television, film and Television Commercial (TVC). TVC is very well known as a tool to promote a wide variety of goods, services and ideas since the dawn of television. The main reason TVC is so effective is the size of the audience it reaches. Nearly every American household has a television. TV has become an integrated part of our lifestyle. From granddads to grandkids, every American watches at least two hours of television a day. This entire television viewing means your commercial is seen more than on any other media. Of course, not everyone viewing your commercial will buy your product. Still, the odds increase with a larger audience. Admittedly,

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Television allows consumers to see and hear a product in operation. It has greater sensory appeal than any other media. Video and audio combined bring your product or service to life. The Internet is a close second in this type of advertising. The difference is; in order to view a full-screen product video, the Internet surfer must actively click on it. Television ads play with no consumer prompting. Unfortunately, this often means the viewer can get up and run to the kitchen or restroom during your commercial. Despite this, most consumers will remain seated for engaging commercials, seeing them as part of the evening's entertainment.

II. PURPOSES OF THE STUDY

The reason that the researchers chose to study how the public relations can recognize non-governmental organization image through TVC because one of the researchers graduated with a masters in documentary film production and has experience in working at Habitat for Humanity Thailand which is a non-governmental organization as a public relation and communications manager. The researchers are well aware of the problems and barriers to making the organization's publicity in this manner; we cannot afford commercial advertising because of where the funding comes from. We need a budget to support the release or cover the media costs because it is relatively high. As morals of foundation, we cannot use the proceeds from donations to be used in advertising, except when donors want to clearly state that the money can spend on public relations programs.

In this research, the pattern of television commercials will enhance the image of a non-governmental organization. The researchers expect that the results of this research will be particularly useful for non-governmental organizations that are interested in promotional TVC, whether funds in production will come from donations or funds of the organization itself. It is worthy enough to do some research before investment.

III. MATERIAL AND LITERATURE

Image is the combination between objective facts and personal judgment, which is a result of the perception of individuals. For example, the image of a university is based on facts about the location, reputation, teachers, students, and so on. For personal judgment, we can ask people who live nearby. We may get a positive answer or negative one, it depends on personal experiences. However, the word **image** has a lot of meaning, but one of the interesting and most meaningful is derived from the importance of the following words.

I = Institution: Create a positive image of the cause reliability. Institutions or organizations must have a logo that is memorable and can be trust in the long run.

M = Management: Administrator, director or manager needs to have intelligence. Performance and experience is recognized and accepted as the general public.

A = Action: A good service and a friendly, caring staff, who do not take advantage from consumers.

G = Goodness: The organization deals with social responsibility (Corporate Social Responsibility, CSR) such as, integrity, straightforwardness, transparency, or contributes to the society in various fields and so on.

E = Employee: Which are like ambassadors of the organization. The employee can enhance the credibility and trust in the organization by building strong relationships with clients, prospects, and to society. [1]

In addition to the meaning of image, it can be described as images that occur in the minds of the people towards the organization including products and services. Therefore, the term of image literally means covering administration, management of an organization and product or service itself. [2] Boulding [3] explained that **image** is subjective knowledge, which consists of facts, interpretations and the behavior that we show out, it depends on the image of the thing that we have in the brain. He has classified the organization image into 4 sections. There are perceptual component, cognitive component, affective component and cognitive component.

Research about television commercials found that TVC could affect emotions, feelings, and behaviors of consumers. TVC is a part in persuading consumers to mimic what was seen in the TVC, especially teenagers. Therefore, TVC is a mass media that can accessible to all ages, can be infused into a consumer's mind and cause consumers to change ideas, attitudes and behavior. However, the amount of influence of TVC depends on the knowledge and experience of the consumer [4].

There are examples of TVC that was created to encourage an organization image. The content is not focused on selling products or services but aim to emphasize brand and make costumers believe that the brand has a social responsibility that is more than the selling purpose [5].

Fig. 1 Regency Thai Brandy's TVC

1. Regency Thai Brandy Co., Ltd.; although the manufacturers sell alcohol, the image of the organization about joining to conserve cultural traditions and the beauty of Thailand, instead of advertising their products.

It helps a lot to build a reputation and give impressions of the products. The consumer can recognize the brand and products through the TVC.

2. Total Access Communication Public Co., Ltd. (DTAC); encouraging young people not to forget their hometown. After graduation should bring their own knowledge to local development.

Fig. 2 DTAC's TVC

3. Toyota Motor Thailand Co., Ltd.: Created TVC under project "White Love White Road", which is about the safety, etiquette and road manners.

Fig. 3 Toyota Motor Thailand's TVC

4. Ministry of Public Health: "Good Health Starts Here", the main concept is to encourage awareness of health issues and starts doing some physical activity to provide greater health and disease prevention.

Fig. 4 Ministry of Public Health's TVC

5. Muang Thai Insurance Public Co., Ltd.: this TVC is based on true story, about poor women who has cancer. She only has 2 years until the end of her life, but life is valuable and precious. She spends the rest of her life to teach children and take care of them. The main idea for this TVC is every life has value in itself.

Fig. 5 Muang Thai Insurance's TVC

According to the examples of TVC above, researchers realized that without any additional products offered, consumers would build up their trust so it is called "Molding Public Opinion". This theory often used in corporate advertising or political advertising. It plays with feelings and opinions, tries to impress by using words or phrases. It is a belief that comes from communication theory called propaganda that made a powerful impact in the World War II. [6] There are popular content of corporate advertising:

- Diversity -A variety of products or services.
- Technology -Researched and quality control.
- Productivity -Increases the capacity of the engine.
- Energy -Conservation of energy.
- Ecology -Natural resources, recycling and air pollution prevention.
- Corporate Social Responsibility -Educational or intellectual sponsoring.
- Major Capital -Protection of consumers.
- Investment -The potential of the investment or expansion.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative research which a combination of two sources are content analysis (documents, literature and relevant research work) and questionnaires that used both close and open ended by spreading out random sampling questionnaire which was made from surveymonkey.com (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/s/JC2JP85>) to collect data from samples, there are students from SuanSunandhaRajabhat University who study in film and media fields, staff who currently work with non-governmental organization and Thai in a total of 100. A questionnaire survey was carried out from 1-28 February 2014.

V. SURVEY RESULTS

The questionnaire is divided into 2 parts. Part A: questions about personal information. Part B: questions about the behavior of interest in watching television commercials and asking about opinions relate to the pattern of television commercials that can encourage the non-governmental organization image. The result of the questionnaire is as following;

Fig. 6 Occupation of samples

Fig. 7 Question: Have you ever seen television commercials of non-profit organization?

Fig. 8 Question: The most important thing that people can recognize the organization image through TVC

Fig. 9 Question: Do you think TVC can affect to recognize the image and affect the donation or get involved with the organization?

The majority of samples come from cooperate employees (34.02%) and followed by students (21.65%), self-employed (18.56%), government officers are equal to NGO's employees (11.34%) and enterprise employees (3.09%). The numbers of 66 samples (68.04%) have seen television commercials of non-profit organization. The largest percentage of the most important thing that can help people recognize the organization image through TVC was performance (72.63%) and followed by ambassador or presenter (20%), reputation (5.26%), CEO is equal to staff (1.05%) and worldwide (0%) was unimportant for people to recognize the organization image.

The researches asked the samples how TVC affect to samples in term of recognize the image and donation or get involved with the organization so result shown that TVC is very effective to recognize the image (54.17%) and effective to donation or get involved with the organization (62.89%). One of the most significant questions to emerge from this survey is that of the opinions about patterns, which samples wish to see in the TVC. The samples want to see reliability and trust of the organization (51.55%) through presentation and how staff are working on filed and performance (31.96%). 12 people (12.37%), they want to see famous person and celebrity appeared in TVC.

VI. CONCLUSION

The results of this study show that TVC affects the organization image. Viewed from Fig. 8, the survey found that people will recognize the image through contributions and also depends on a person who represents an organization, which may be a celebrity or famous person. However, a positive image always comes from ambassador or presenter who behaves well and does not do any damage, because that will affect the organization as well.

The reason that the researchers select a variety samples, because researchers would like to see how TVC can convince people who can remain as donors to donate or give a hand to organizations. Moreover, staffs that work in organizations that they want to communicate with other people through TVC. The recognition of the organization image can affect

donations and contribution of donors. This is beneficial to the organization because if donors can remember the organization, feel familiar and trust. It can reach out and support without any doubt.

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